

**A CASE OF TYPE 1 NEUROFIBROMATOSIS WITH
CORPUS CALLOSUM AGENESIS****Hanife Merve Akca¹**¹Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University, 70100, Karaman, Turkey**ABSTRACT**

Erythema multiforme (EM) is an acute inflammatory hypersensitivity reaction involving the skin and mucous membranes that develops due to infection and drugs and can be seen at any age. Although it is mostly a self-limiting disease, it has a distribution that can go up to the formation of Stevens Johnson Syndrome (SJS) and toxic epidermal necrolysis (TEN). A seven-year-old male patient applied with the complaint of rash on the face and hands that started 2 days ago. The patient was diagnosed with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (DM) at the age of 2 years and had therefore been using 1U/kg/day insulin (short-medium-acting) for 5 years. On physical examination, his general condition was good, and his body temperature was 36.5 °C. There were typical and atypical target lesions on the cheeks and erythematous maculopapular lesions on the dorsum of the hand. The patient was diagnosed with erythema multiforme developing after herpes simplex. In the treatment, oral valacyclovir at a dose of 20 mg/kg/day 2x1 for 5 days and topical corticosteroids were planned on the lesions. Oral care solutions containing antihistamine for itching and analgesic for oral lesions were given. The patient's skin and mucosal lesions began to regress on the 3rd day after treatment.

Key Words: *Erythema multiforme, Diabetes Mellitus, Valacyclovir*

INTRODUCTION

Erythema multiforme (EM) is an acute inflammatory hypersensitivity reaction involving the skin and mucous membranes that develops due to infection and drugs and can be seen at any age. Although it is mostly a self-limiting disease, it has a distribution that can go up to the formation of Stevens Johnson Syndrome (SJS) and toxic epidermal necrolysis (TEN) (1, 2). Herpes simplex virus (HSV) is known to be the most common cause of recurrent types among infectious agents in etiology.

CASE

A seven-year-old male patient applied with the complaint of rash on the face and hands that started 2 days ago. It was learned that these complaints had recurred from time to time for six

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676588

months, and vesicles had formed on the lips before. The patient was diagnosed with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (DM) at the age of 2 years and had therefore been using 1U/kg/day insulin (short-medium-acting) for 5 years. There was no history of recent infection or vaccination. On physical examination, his general condition was good, and his body temperature was 36.5 °C. There were typical and atypical target lesions on the cheeks and erythematous maculopapular lesions on the dorsum of the hand (Fig 1 and Fig 2). Minimal crusting was observed on the lips. In the laboratory examination, complete blood count, peripheral smear, electrolyte and transaminase levels, kidney function tests, sedimentation rate, complete urine analysis and viral serological examination were normal. The patient was diagnosed with erythema multiforme developing after herpes simplex. In the treatment, oral valacyclovir at a dose of 20 mg/kg/day 2x1 for 5 days and topical corticosteroids were planned on the lesions. Oral care solutions containing antihistamine for itching and analgesic for oral lesions were given. The patient's skin and mucosal lesions began to regress on the 3rd day after treatment.

Fig. 1. Papules and plaques with erythema around the face, some in the form of typical targets

Fig 2. Atypical target lesions on the dorsum of the hand

DISCUSSION

Erythema multiforme (EM) is a mucocutaneous hypersensitivity reaction characterized by target lesions on the skin. It is examined in two subgroups depending on whether there is mucosal involvement: While no involvement is found in the EM minor subgroup, EM major is characterized by mucosal involvement. HSV infection is the most common cause of EM minor development. HSV-associated EM occurs within days or weeks following HSV infection. Both types of HSV (types 1-2) have been associated with EM. The lip is the region where lesions are most common (3). In our case, we observed that target lesions were formed on the extremities two days after vesicular lesions appeared on the lip. As in our case, the lesions can be seen as papules in EM minor, or they can enlarge and form typical target lesions characterized by erythema surrounding the pale area in the middle. 20-60% of patients diagnosed with EM in the pediatric and adult groups are defined as EM major. Oral mucosal involvement is the most common in this group (4,5). In EM minor, where mucosal involvement is not usually seen, skin lesions are generally in the extremities and have a symmetrical distribution. The dorsum of the hand, palms, and soles are frequently involved (6). In addition, erosive lichen planus, pemphigus, chicken pox, stomatitis, herpetic gingivostomatitis, Kawasaki syndrome, drug eruption, acute hemorrhagic

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edema should be considered in the differential diagnosis of patients with EM major (7). EM is rarely seen in children and often occurs due to infection. EM can be very mild as a minor, or it can be fatal at a rate of 5-15%, such as Steven-Johnson syndrome. An increase in HSV-1-related entities has been reported in adult patients with type 1 DM (8, 9). Although there is not enough data in pediatric cases, since we think that it may be a trigger for the development of erythema multiforme after herpes labialis, Type 1 DM should be considered as one of the possible causes in pediatric patients with EM, along with other reasons, and the patient should be examined in this regard.

REFERENCES

1. Odom RB, James WD, Berger TG: Diseases of the skin. 9^{uncu} Baskı. Philadelphia. W.B. Saunders Company, 2000;146-171.
2. Ayangco L, Rogers RS 3rd: Oral manifestations of erythema multiforme. *Dermatol Clin* 2003;21:195-205.[*J Dermatol*. 2006;212:168-76.
3. Ayangco L, Rogers RS 3rd. Oral manifestations of erythema multiforme. *Dermatol Clin* 2003; 21:195.
4. Sokumbi O, Wetter DA. Clinical features, diagnosis, and treatment of erythema multiforme: a review for the practicing dermatologist. *Int J Dermatol* 2012;51(8):889-902.
5. Sanchis JM, Bagán JV, Gavaldá C, Murillo J, Diaz JM. Erythema multiforme: diagnosis, clinical manifestations and treatment in a retrospective study of 22 patients. *J Oral Pathol Med* 2010;39(10):747-52.
6. Carder KR. Hypersensitivity reactions in neonates and infants. *Dermatol Ther* 2005;18:160-75.
7. Krippaehne JA, Montgomery MT. Erythema multiforme: a literature review and case report. *Spec Care Dentist* 1992;12:125.
8. S. Yuhua, W. Yongjian, P. Weidong and Y. Yuejin. An association of herpes simplex virus Type 1 infection with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 28(2), 2005, 435 – 436.
9. A. J. Oke, A. A. Oke Herpes Simplex (Hsv–1, 2) Seropositivity: A Study Carried Out Among Diabetic and Non-Diabetic Patients in A Community In Southwest Nigeria. *J Dent and Med S* ,13 (1), 2014, 53-55.